

Complexation ion exchange electrochromatography of metal ions on papers impregnated with titanium(IV) tungstate

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The electrochromatographic behaviour of 37 metal ions has been studied on titanium(IV) tungstate papers using oxalic, citric, tartaric, hydrochloric and nitric acids as background electrolytes. The ion exchange capacity of these papers is determined and their selectivity for different metal ions discussed. The mechanism of migration is explained. Prediction of elution sequence of metal ions on the basis of their migration is also checked. A number of useful binary and ternary separations are achieved.

Electrochromatography of metal ions has been extensively applied in order to achieve difficult separations¹. If electrochromatographic migration is combined with ion exchange and complexation, more interesting results are achieved and the potential of this technique increases considerably². However, very few studies^{3,4} have been reported using papers impregnated with inorganic ion exchangers for electrochromatography of metal ions in simple aqueous media. Recently, electrochromatographic behaviour of some metal ions has been studied on Zr^{IV} phosphoantimonate papers⁵ in complex forming acids and their salt solutions. We have also studied the reversed phase thin layer chromatography of metal ions in oxalic acid-oxalate media⁶.

Among the various inorganic ion-exchangers, tungstates have been found to be quite stable in acids. Literature survey reveals that titanium(IV) tungstate exhibits good ion exchange properties⁷⁻¹⁰ and shows high selectivity and stability at low pH. Hence, weak complexing acids such as oxalic, citric and tartaric were taken as background electrolytes so as to prevent the hydrolysis of the exchange material. As a result of the combined effect of the electric field, ion exchange and complexation, a number of analytically important and useful binary and ternary separations of metal ions have been achieved.

Results and Discussion

Electrochromatography of 37 metal ions on titanium(IV) tungstate papers has been performed in the following background electrolytes: 0.1 M oxalic acid (O.A.), 0.1 M citric acid (C.A.), 0.1 M tartaric acid (T.A.), HCl (0.00001, 0.0001, 0.001, 0.01, 0.1 and 1 M) and HNO₃ (0.00001, 0.0001, 0.001, 0.01, 0.1 and 1 M). The movement of the centre of the zones was measured in cm. A positive sign in-

dicates the movement of the ions towards cathode and a negative sign the movement of the ions towards anode. The electrochromatographic migrations of all the metal ions are given in Table 1. On the basis of the difference in migration and the direction of movement of metal ions, several important binary, ternary and quaternary separations were achieved (Table 2). In order to study the effect of ion exchange on the mobility of metal ions, Whatman No. 1 papers were also used for comparison. It is apparent that the background electrolyte and the impregnating material are both responsible for separations. Aqueous HCl and HNO₃ of different concentrations were also used as background electrolytes to study the effect of pH on the mobility of metal ions. For complexation effect, migration of all the metal ions was noted in non-complexing aqueous HNO₃ media of same pH as that of the complexing acids.

In order to bring out some interesting points of these studies, migration of metal ions has been plotted against their atomic numbers in citric acid, tartaric acid and oxalic acid media. The figures are not given for the sake of brevity. It was observed that for citric acid, the figure appears to be a nice periodic curve with alkali metals and Tl^I occupying the maxima.

In case of oxalic acid, the monovalent metal ions such as K^I, Cs^I and Tl^I occupy the maxima and most of the metal ions have zero-migration because oxalic acid is a good precipitating agent. It is used to precipitate thorium and lanthanones from monozite⁸. This is evident from the fact that these metal ions have zero-migration in oxalic acid media. It is known that Hg^{II} forms stronger complexes than Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}, which explains the higher migration of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} than in case of Hg^{II}. In oxalic acid media UO₂^{II} forms anionic complexes of the type [UO₂(C₂O₄)₂]²⁻ or [UO₂(C₂O₄)₂]⁴⁻ and moves towards anode⁹. The same is

Table 1. Migration (cm) of metal ions in various electrolytes on titanium(IV) tungstate papers

Time = 3 h; Voltage applied = 100 V

Metal ions	HCl (M)						HNO ₃ (M)						O.A.	C.A.	
	1	0.1	0.01	0.001	0.0001	0.00001	1	0.1	0.01	0.001	0.0001	0.00001			0.1 M
Al ^{III}	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	N.D.	+0.5	+1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	+1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	+2.0
K ^I	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	+2.0	+3.0	0.0	N.D.	N.D.	+2.5	+1.0	N.D.	0.0	+3.0	+2.0	+2.5
Cs ^I	+2.0	+4.0	+2.0	-1.5	+2.5	+3.0	+1.5	+4.0	+2.0	+2.0	+3.5	+1.0	+1.5	+4.0	+2.0
Ba ^{II}	+2.0	+5.5	+1.0	0.0	-1.2	+0.5	+1.5	+2.5	+1.0	-1.0	+2.0	+1.0	+0.5	+2.0	+0.5
Sr ^{II}	N.D.	+4.5	+2.5	0.0	0.0	+1.5	+1.0	+2.5	+3.5	+2.0	+4.0	+1.0	0.0	+2.5	+2.0
Ca ^{II}	N.D.	+1.5	N.D.	+1.5	+1.5	0.0	-2.5	-1.5	+4.0	+2.0	0.0	+3.0	+2.0	0.0	+1.0
Cr ^{III}	+1.0	+2.0	0.0	0.0	+1.0	0.0	+1.0	+2.5	+1.5	+3.0	+2.5	N.D.	+1.0	+0.5	+1.0
Zn ^{II}	0.0	+5.0	0.0	+1.0	0.0	0.0	N.D.	+2.5	+2.0	+3.0	+2.0	+0.5	+1.5	+3.0	0.0
Mn ^{II}	+1.0	+2.4	+2.0	-1.5	+2.0	+1.5	+1.5	+1.5	+3.0	+4.0	+1.0	0.0	0.0	+1.0	+2.0
Mo ^{VI}	0.0	N.D.	+2.0	N.D.	N.D.	-3.5	+1.0	+2.0	+1.0	-1.0	+1.5	0.0	+3.0	-1.5	0.0
Se ^{IV}	0.0	0.0	0.0	N.D.	+0.5	-2.5	0.0	+1.0	+1.5	0.0	+1.5	0.0	N.D.	-1.4	+2.0
Ag ^I	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	+1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Pb ^{II}	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	+2.5	0.0	+1.0	+1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Cd ^{II}	-1.2	+2.0	+1.6	+2.0	+2.0	0.0	+1.0	+3.0	+2.5	+3.0	-1.0	+1.5	0.0	+1.0	+2.0
Hg ₂ ^{II}	-1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	+2.5	0.0	0.0	+1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	+1.0	0.0
Hg ^{II}	-2.5	0.0	-2.0	0.0	0.0	-1.5	-1.0	-2.0	+2.0	+1.0	+1.0	+2.0	0.0	+2.0	0.0
Co ^{II}	0.0	+3.5	+3.0	+3.0	+1.0	0.0	+4.0	-5.0	+4.0	+1.0	+1.0	0.0	0.0	+3.0	0.0
Ni ^{II}	0.0	+4.5	+1.5	+4.0	0.0	+2.0	+1.0	+2.0	+1.0	+1.0	+3.0	+1.0	-5.0	+2.5	+2.0
Cu ^{II}	+1.0	+2.6	+2.0	+1.0	-1.0	0.0	+1.5	+4.5	0.0	+2.0	0.0	+3.0	-1.0	0.0	0.0
Tl ^I	0.0	+3.0	-1.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	+2.0	+1.0	+2.5	-1.0	-1.0	0.0	+6.0	+5.5	+2.0
Pd ^{II}	-3.5	-3.5	-2.0	-1.0	-1.5	-1.0	-3.0	-3.0	+1.0	-1.0	-1.0	0.0	0.0	-2.5	-3.0
Ru ^{III}	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-1.0
Ce ^{III}	+1.5	+5.5	0.0	+1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	+3.5	+1.0	+3.0	+2.5	+1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0
Ce ^{IV}	0.0	+1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	+2.0	-2.0	+4.0	+1.0	+0.5	+0.5	N.D.	0.0	0.0
Pr ^{III}	+3.0	+5.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	+1.5	+3.5	-1.0	+3.0	+0.5	0.0	0.0	+0.6	0.0
Nd ^{III}	0.0	+2.0	0.0	0.0	+2.0	0.0	+1.2	+6.5	0.0	+3.0	+3.5	+2.0	0.0	+1.0	0.0
Sm ^{III}	+2.0	+1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	+1.3	+5.0	0.0	+2.0	+2.5	+1.0	-1.0	0.0	0.0
Th ^{IV}	+1.5	+2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	+1.5	+2.0	0.0	+4.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
UO ₂ ^{II}	+1.5	+2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	+1.0	+1.0	+1.5	+1.0	0.0	+2.0	+1.0	-1.0	-1.0	-1.5
VO ^{II}	+1.4	+5.5	+2.0	+1.0	+1.5	+1.8	+1.5	+1.0	-2.5	+1.0	+2.0	+1.5	+2.2	0.0	0.0
Zr ^{IV}	+1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	+1.0	+1.0	+2.0	0.0	0.0	+2.5	0.0	N.D.	0.0
La ^{III}	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	+3.0	+1.0	+4.0	+4.0	0.0	-1.5	+1.0	0.0
Sn ^{II}	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Sb ^{III}	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	+1.5	+2.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Bi ^{III}	-2.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-2.0	-1.0	0.0
Fe ^{III}	+1.5	+2.0	+1.2	+3.0	0.0	0.0	+1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	+1.0	+1.0	-3.5	+1.0	-1.5
Fe ^{II}	+1.0	+5.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	+1.0	+2.0	0.0	+2.0	+1.0	0.0	+1.0	+3.0	+1.5

N.D. = Not detected.

Table 2. Important separations of metal ions on titanium(IV) tungstate papers

Electrolytes	Separation
1 M HNO ₃	Ag ^I (0.0) - Pd ^{II} (-3.0), Ni ^{II} (+1.0) - Pd ^{II} (-3.0), Ca ^{II} (-2.5) - Sr ^{II} (+1.0)
0.1 M HNO ₃	Ag ^I (0.0) - Cu ^{II} (+4.5), Ni ^{II} (+2.0) - Co ^{II} (-5.0), Ce ^{III} (+3.5) - Ce ^{IV} (-2.0)
0.01 M HNO ₃	VO ^{II} (-2.5) - UO ₂ ^{II} (+1.5)
0.001 M HNO ₃	Al ^{III} (0.0) - Mn ^{II} (+4.0), Ba ^{II} (-1.0) - Sr ^{II} (+3.5), Zr ^{IV} (0.0) - Th ^{IV} (+4.5)
0.0001 M HNO ₃	Th ^{IV} (0.0) or Zr ^{IV} (0.0) - La ^{III} (+4.0), Cd ^{II} (0.0) - Ni ^{II} (+3.0)
1 M HCl	Ag ^I (0.0) - Pd ^{II} (-3.5)
0.1 M HCl	Pd ^{II} (-3.5) - Zn ^{II} (+5.0)
0.001 M HCl	Cs ^I (+1.5) - K ^I (-2.0)
0.0001 M HCl	Bi ^{III} (0.0) - Cu ^{II} (-1.0) - Cd ^{II} (+2.0)
0.00001 M HCl	Hg ^{II} (-1.5) - Hg ₂ ^{II} (+2.5)
0.1 M Oxalic acid	Ag ^I (0.0) - Tl ^I (+6.0)

true for citric acid and tartaric acid media. In tartaric acid K^I, Cs^I and Tl^I show higher migration. Pd^{II}, UO₂^{II}, Ru^{III} and Fe^{III} move towards anode thereby confirming the formation of anionic species.

The average mobility (*M*) of the metal ion was found to increase with the increase in ionisation constant (*K_a*) of the acids used as background electrolytes which is in the order, T.A. < C.A. < O.A. This is probably due to the increase in number of the H⁺ ions competing with the metal ions for the exchange site.

Regarding the mobility of the metal ions it was found to decrease with the increase of the charge on the metal ions. In citric acid media, the migration decreases in the order, Cs^I > Ba^{II} > La^{III} > Ce^{IV} and Tl^I > Pb^{II} > Bi^{III} > Th^{IV}.

Similarly, in oxalic acid media, the order is found to be $K^I > Ca^{II} > Cr^{III}$. Thus, mobility-charge relationship is true for majority of the metal ions in all background electrolytes. The same trend was observed on Whatman No. 1 papers. This is probably because the metal ions with a higher charge are more strongly adsorbed on the papers and hence move less. Further, the majority of metal ions move towards cathode showing that either they remain as the cationic species or form positively charged complexes with various acids used.

To study the effect of pH on the mobility of ions, aqueous HCl and HNO_3 with varying concentrations were used as background electrolytes. The plots of average mobility of metal ions versus pH (Fig. 1) show that the average mobility is much lower in aqueous HCl media in the pH range 2-4, probably because of the formation of the less mobile chloro-complexes. The average mobility is maximum at pH 1 for both the electrolytes which, however, decreases sharply at pH 2 using aqueous HCl as the medium. Beyond pH 2, there is a gradual decrease in average mobility with an increase in pH. However, in aqueous HNO_3 media the behaviour of metal ions is somewhat different. From pH 1 to 2, the average mobility

Fig. 1. Plots of average mobility vs pH of (●) HCl and (○) HNO_3 .
decreases to a lesser extent. In the pH range 2-4, the mobility remains almost constant but again there is a sharp decrease as we proceed from pH 4 to 5

Fig. 2 shows average mobility of metal ions on Whatman No. 1 and titanium(IV) tungstate papers at different pH in aqueous HNO_3 media. It is observed that the average mobility on Whatman No. 1 papers is much higher than that on impregnated ones. This is because of the fact that tungstates of most of the metal ions are less soluble than the corresponding nitrates and chlorides. In case of Pb^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Fe^{III} and Zn^{II} , the difference in migration is much higher as these metal ions are strongly adsorbed on impregnated papers. The higher distribution coefficient (K_d) for these metal ions on titanium(IV) tungstate¹⁰ supports this view.

Fig. 2. Plots of average mobility vs HNO_3 on (○) titanium(IV) tungstate and (*) Whatman no 1 papers

The K_d values and the electrochromatographic migration of some metal ions are given in Table 3. It is observed that the sequence of K_d values is the same as the one predicted from electrochromatographic migrations. K_d values : $Ca^{II} < Sr^{II} < Zn = Mn^{II} < Zr^{IV}$; electrochromatographic migration : $Ca^{II} > Mn^{II} > Sr^{II} > Zn^{II} > Zr^{IV}$.

Table 3. K_d values and electrochromatographic migration of metal ions in 0.01 M HNO_3

Metal ion	K_d "	Migration cm
Ca^{II}	0.04	4.0
Sr^{II}	0.12	3.5
Mn^{II}	0.25	3.0
Zn^{II}	0.25	2.0
Zr^{IV}	1.30	1.0

"Ref 8.

Ions which have a zero-migration may do so owing to (i) precipitation, (ii) ion exchange, (iii) complexation to form uncharged complexes and (iv) strong adsorption owing to the high charge. On mixing solution of metal ion and sodium tungstate followed by 0.1 M oxalic acid, a precipitate was obtained for Sr^{II}, Co^{II}, Ag^I, Pb^{II}, Sb^{III}, Ce^{III}, Th^{IV}, Pr^{III}, Ru^{III} and Zr^{IV}. For these metal ions, zero-migration in 0.1 M oxalic acid is due to precipitation. For other electrolytes also several metal ions were precipitated under these conditions (Table 4). Thus for all these metal ions the precipitation mechanism holds good.

Table 4. Precipitation of metal ions from solution after addition of sodium tungstate solution followed by electrolyte

Electrolyte	Metal ions Precipitated	Metal ions Not precipitated
1 M HCl	Ni ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Al ^{III} , Zn ^{II} , Nd ^{III} , Ru ^{III} , Sb ^{III} , Ti ^I , Pb ^{II} , Sn ^{II} , Ag ^I	Ce ^{IV}
0.1 M HCl	Al ^{III} , Ru ^{III} , Zr ^{IV} , Bi ^{III} , Ag ^I , Sb ^{III} , Sn ^{II}	Hg ^{II} , Pb ^{II}
0.01 M HCl	Hg ^{II} , Sb ^{III} , Ag ^I , Fe ^{II} , Th ^{IV} , Sm ^{III} , Pr ^{III} , Nd ^{III} , Ru ^{III} , Ce ^{III} , Al ^{III} , Cr ^{III}	Bi ^{III} , Pb ^{II} , Sn ^{II} , Zr ^{IV} , Zn ^{II} , Ce ^{IV}
0.001 M HCl	Cd ^{II} , Ti ^I , Pb ^{II} , Bi ^{III} , Sb ^{III} , Ag ^I , Th ^{IV} , Sm ^{III} , Pr ^{III} , Nd ^{III} , Ce ^{IV} , Ru ^{III}	Hg ^{II} , Hg ^{II}
0.0001 M HCl	Th ^{IV} , Sm ^{III} , Ce ^{III} , Cd ^{II} , Pr ^{III} , Ru ^{III} , Fe ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , Al ^{III} , Sr ^{II} , Ag ^I , Sb ^{III} , UO ²⁺ , Zr ^{IV}	Ce ^{IV} , Hg ^{II} , Pb ^{II} , Bi ^{III}
0.00001 M HCl	Th ^{IV} , Ca ^{II} , Ce ^{III} , Pr ^{III} , Sm ^{III} , Nd ^{III} , Zr ^{IV} , Ru ^{III} , Cr ^{III} , Co ^{II} , K ^I , Cd ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Sb ^{III} , Bi ^{III} , Ag ^I , Sn ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , Fe ^{II}	Ce ^{IV} , Zn ^{II} , Pb ^{II}
1 M HNO ₃	Cd ^{II} , Hg ^{II} , Ag ^I , Bi ^{III} , Sb ^{III} , Pb ^{II}	Se ^{IV}
0.1 M HNO ₃	Ag ^I , Hg ^{II} , Bi ^{III} , Al ^{III} , Sn ^{II} , Fe ^{III}	None
0.01 M HNO ₃	Bi ^{III} , Sn ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Al ^{III} , Fe ^{III} , Fe ^{II} , Nd ^{III} , Th ^{IV} , Sm ^{III}	Pb ^{II}
0.001 M HNO ₃	Hg ^{II} , Bi ^{III} , Sn ^{II} , Sb ^{III} , Al ^{III} , Zr ^{IV}	Se ^{IV}
0.0001 M HNO ₃	Th ^{IV} , Zr ^{IV} , Ca ^{II} , Hg ^{II} , Bi ^{III} , Cu ^{II}	None
0.00001 M HNO ₃	K ^I , Th ^{IV} , Pr ^{III} , Ru ^{III} , Al ^{III} , Co ^{II} , Fe ^{II} , Hg ^{II} , Ti ^I , Pd ^{II} , Pb ^{II} , Bi ^{III} , Sb ^{III} , Sn ^{II}	Mn ^{II}
0.1 M Oxalic acid	Sr ^{II} , Pr ^{III} , Ce ^{III} , Co ^{II} , Ag ^I , Pb ^{II} , Sb ^{III} , Sn ^{II} , Ru ^{III} , Zr ^{IV}	Mn ^{II} , Pd ^{II} , Hg ^{II}
0.1 M Oxalic acid	Hg ^{II} , Ag ^I , Sb ^{III} , Pb ^{II} , Al ^{III} , Th ^{IV} , Sm ^{III} , Ce ^{III} , Ca ^{II} , VO ^{II}	Cu ^{II} , Ce ^{IV}
0.1 M Tartaric acid	Hg ^{II} , Ag ^I , Sb ^{III} , Bi ^{III} , Pb ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , VO ^{II} , Zr ^{IV} , Pr ^{III} , Sm ^{III} , Nd ^{III} , Th ^{IV} , Ce ^{III}	Ce ^{IV} , Zn ^{II} , Mo ^{VI}

Experimental

Electrochromatographic studies were performed on Whatman No. 1 paper strips (46.4 × 2.75 cm) using a horizontal electrophoresis apparatus operated with an electronic regulated power supply unit (Matrex Ltd., India). Whatman No. 1 paper strips were impregnated with 0.25 M solutions of both titanium(IV) chloride (Reidal) and sodium tungstate (A.R.). These paper strips were found to possess considerable ion exchange capacity. For K⁺ ion (K⁺-H⁺ exchange) the ion exchange capacity was found to be 0.35 mequiv/g of treated paper as determined by column experiments (saturation method).

Solutions of metal ions and detection reagents were prepared and used as described earlier³.

Electrochromatographic studies were performed by the method already described³. In all cases, electrochromatography was continued for 3 h at a constant potential difference of 100 V. There was no significant heating during the process.

References

- "Inorganic Ion Exchange Materials", ed. A. Clearfield, CRC Press, Boca Raton, 1982; K. G. Varshney and A. Mohammad in "Handbook of Thin-layer Chromatography", eds. J. Sherma and B. Fried. Marcel Dekker, New York, 1990; R. Kuroda and M. P. Volynets in "CRC Handbook of Chromatography : Inorganics", ed. M. Qureshi, CRC Press, Boca Raton, 1987; K. G. Varshney, "Synthetic Inorganic Ion Exchangers in Chemical Analysis", CRC Press, Boca Raton, 1990.
- M. Qureshi and S. D. Sharma, *Sep. Sci. Technol.*, 1978, 13, 723; S. D. Sharma, S. Misra and T. R. Sharma, *Anal. Chim.*, 1985, 75, 145.
- S. D. Sharma and S. Misra, *J. Planar Chromatogr.*, 1989, 2, 399.
- U. A. Th. Brinkman, R. W. Giese, J. K. Haken and L. R. Snyder, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1994, 681, B92, 212, 332.
- A. K. Misra, *J. Planar Chromatogr.*, 1998, 11, 56.
- S. D. Sharma and S. C. Sharma, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1999, 841, 263.
- M. Qureshi and J. P. Gupta, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, 1755.
- R. Belcher and C. L. Wilson, "New Methods in Analytical Chemistry", 2nd. ed., Asia Publishing House, New Delhi, 1956.
- A. A. Grinberg, "An Introduction to the Chemistry of Complex Compounds", Addison-Wesley, Reading, 1962.
- M. Qureshi, N. Zehra, S. A. Nabi and V. Kumar, *Talanta*, 1973, 20, 609.